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Title: The Ethics of Representing Perpetrators in Documentaries on Genocide

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Abstract

Current discourse on the representation of genocide claims that we are currently experiencing “the shift from the era of the witness to the era of the perpetrator” (Morag, 2020: 3). This raises ethical concerns over why and how documentaries engage with perpetrators. Based on an assessment of 203 documentaries on 7 genocides, my paper makes three kinds of contribution in addressing these concerns: 1) It discusses the ethics of representing perpetrators in archival footage, reenactments, or interviews in a wider corpus than those covered in recent discussions (Canet, 2019; Morag, 2020). 2) It uncovers a broad range of ethical reasons for why documentary filmmakers engage with perpetrators, rather than seeking to establish a singular ethical ground for this engagement. This approach can do better justice to the varying cultural, historical, and political contexts of the respective genocides, the different production contexts and target audiences of the documentaries, and the different styles and types of documentaries that inform the ethics of perpetrator representation. 3) It introduces two broad categories of perpetrator representation in documentaries that conceptualize the ethical purposes of this engagement differently.

The Ethics of Representing Genocidal Perpetrators

Current discourse on the representation of genocide claims that we are experiencing “the shift from the era of the witness to the era of the perpetrator” (Morag, 2020: 3). While in the past documentaries on genocide included occasional, and usually brief, interviews of perpetrators, in recent decades “there has been a considerable increase in the number of narratives exploring these [20th and 21st century] atrocities from the perpetrators’ perspective,” as media scholar Fernando Canet avers (Canet, 2019: 805). This new corpus of documentaries is particularly remarkable for its sustained engagement of individual perpetrators *as individuals* and detailed accounts of their experiences, often through face-to-face encounters with the filmmakers, who in turn frequently come from the victim community or are closely affiliated with it.

This recent trend in documentary filmmaking prompts Canet to ask “why should we engage with perpetrators?” (2019: 805) given the problematic actions and perspectives of the perpetrators. However, it seems to me a limited understanding of the question when its answer is sought only by looking at recent documentaries featuring perpetrator interviews – for few are the documentaries on genocide that do not “engage with perpetrators” on some level. In fact, documentary engagements with perpetrators abound – especially perpetrators in the highest echelons of power, including figures like Hitler and Himmler – and have been around for many decades preceding recent trends. Thus, even if the documentaries discussed by Canet and Morag press the question of why to engage with perpetrators with particular urgency, a full answer to the question needs to cast the net more widely. For why should documentaries – ever – engage with and represent perpetrators in any form?

In engaging with this principal question, we must also ask: Do different ethical questions of representing perpetrators emerge with regard to the respective states of justice post-genocide (from full scale immunity to maximal prosecution)? Are there different ethical requirements pertaining to the type of footage of perpetrators (e.g. archival footage or interviews with perpetrators)? And what bearing do the cultural background of the director(s) (e.g. member of the victim community or Euro-American filmmakers filming in developing countries) and target audience have on the ethics of representing perpetrators?

In order to answer these questions I gathered a growing corpus of 203 documentaries (counting series as one) on seven genocides (the Herero & Nama genocide, the Armenian genocide, the Holocaust, the Indonesian 1965-66 genocide, the Cambodian genocide, the Rwandan genocide, the Bosnian genocide). Documentaries were selected if they represented perpetrators through interviews, archival footage, or reenactments. Overwhelmingly the corpus of documentaries was compiled from academic filmographies. To track down Rwandan productions, some of which were difficult to find in Europe, I traveled to Rwanda and interviewed filmmakers and producers to get an overview over and access to local productions. While I acquired especially older productions as DVDs, an astonishing amount of documentaries is available online, YouTube being the most commonly used platform. In my analysis of the documentaries, I summarize the overall sequence of narrated events, the footage used, and salient features of editing, cinematography, and audio. Each summary runs between a few hundred to a few thousand words per documentary. The earliest film is from 1945 and the most recent from 2022, encompassing both feature and television documentaries. More documentaries in the corpus are about the Holocaust (~51%) than all other genocides combined and due to the prevalence of docuseries the Holocaust makes up around 63% of the aggregated duration. My corpus is limited to films in English, French, and German or with subtitles in those languages. Most of my search and acquisition efforts are dedicated to genocides other than the Holocaust and, unlike in the case of the Holocaust, I include documentary shorts (~20-30 minutes) concerning other genocides, especially if they are (co-)productions from the country of the genocide.

While taking into account above limitations, my corpus gives a comprehensive picture of genocide documentary production and is in a unique position to tackle the ethical questions arising from the representation of perpetrators. My paper makes three kinds of contribution: 1) It discusses the ethics of representing perpetrators in a wider corpus than those covered in recent discussions (Canet, 2019; Morag, 2020). 2) It uncovers a broad range of ethical reasons for why documentary filmmakers engage with perpetrators, rather than seeking to establish a singular ethical ground for this engagement (such as pursuing a quasi-linear path towards reconciliation in Canet, 2019; or confronting perpetrators with victims' resentment in Morag, 2020). This approach can do better justice to the varying cultural, historical, and political contexts of the respective genocides, the different production contexts and target audiences of the documentaries, and the different styles and types of documentaries that inform the ethics of perpetrator representation. 3) It introduces two broad categories of perpetrator representation in documentaries that conceptualize the ethical purposes of this engagement.

I proceed first by a principal discussion of why, ethically, perpetrators can and should be engaged with by documentary filmmakers and then characterize two broad types of documentary perpetrator engagement. The first of these two types is what I call historiographical documentaries that aim to give an historical account of the respective genocide's history, including its perpetrators. Historiographical documentaries tend to focus on major perpetrators, make extensive use of archival footage (frequently shot by perpetrators) and short perpetrator interviews, and typically ethically

motivate their filmic quest by aiming to foster public understanding. Subsequently, I examine what I call testimonial documentaries, often filmed in contexts of transitional justice, which feature perpetrator testimonies and confessions more extensively and typically frame them not in terms of a concluded past but as an unfolding present these perpetrator engagements themselves are part of and help shape.

The Ethics and the “why” of engaging with perpetrators

The question of why engage with perpetrators has been asked before and it has also been answered many times in different discursive and disciplinary contexts. Historians and social psychologists seeking to examine the causes and consequences of genocide inevitably rely in their arguments on close examination of documents and statements by perpetrators. Here, the question as to why engage with perpetrators is equally inevitably answered by a need to understand the causal drivers of perpetration in order to prevent future genocides.¹ Perhaps Timothy Snyder puts it most succinctly: “It is less appealing, but morally more urgent, to understand the actions of the perpetrators. The moral danger, after all, is never that one might become a victim but that one might be a perpetrator or a bystander” (2022: 376). Indeed, as Gerhard Paul’s historiographical account of perpetrator research demonstrates, the facile criminalization and diabolization in historical and legal discourses of a small but ostensible stratum of perpetrators contributed not only to an overall lack of detailed engagement with perpetrators (especially in Germany), but also an exculpation of large swathes of bystanders and perpetrator groups excluded from the narrow representation of perpetrators (2002: 16–20). No doubt, it is, above all, an ethical imperative to avoid such easy exculpation through a detailed engagement with perpetrators.

There is a lively discussion on the related problem of how to engage, if at all, with perpetrator footage and photos in an overall discursive context focused on the Holocaust. Here, the controversies revolve around a “Nazi gaze” supposedly inhering in the photos and films shot by perpetrators, who used this footage as an ultimate enactment of their power over their victims, and whether re-contextualization of this footage can sufficiently counteract this victimizing gaze (see e.g. Hirsch, 2003; Linfield, 2012; Struk, 2004). Yet, much like the historians who can cite documents – that may have initially signaled triumph to an audience believing in perpetrator ideology (say the 1942 Stahlecker report of the “successful” murder of Jews in the Baltics, especially Estonia that was then said to be free of Jews) – for purposes of giving historical, legal, and, ultimately, moral evidence against perpetrators, photos and footage of perpetration can be used to counteract their original purpose. “Every image of suffering says not only, ‘This is so,’ but also, by implication: ‘This must not be’” (Linfield, 2012: 33). Although, no doubt, the re-contextualization can uncritically reproduce victimization,² perpetrators’ enactments and reenactments of their power over victims can be counteracted, as for example in Joshua Oppenheimer’s documentary *The Act of Killing* (2012) (Koch, 2022), just as perpetrators’ denialist, boastful, or even sadistic testimonies can be channeled in positive ways by human rights communities who can use the publicity of such confessions as

¹ To name just few among innumerable others: Browning, 2001: xviii; Lifton, 1988: xi; Waller, 2002: xiv, 2016: xii.

² See Prager’s discussion of Erwin Leiser’s, among others, problematic use of the Warsaw ghetto footage shot by the Nazis in the documentary *Mein Kampf (Den blodiga tiden, 1961)* (Prager, 2015: 202). Nonetheless, Prager argues that documentaries like *The Photographer (Fotoamator, 1998)* and *A Film Unfinished (Shtikat haarchion, 2010)* successfully undermine the perpetrator gaze (2015: 187–224). See also Kantsteiner’s more nuanced discussion of Knopp’s aesthetics that has been accused of fascist tendencies (Kantsteiner, 2003: 644–648)

occasions to contest these narratives, condemn cruelty, and advocate human rights (Payne, 2008: 75–172). Indeed, given that these perpetrator images exist and sympathizers (say Neo-Nazis) will unavoidably continue using them for further victimization, it seems ethically imperative to establish a discourse that re-contextualizes the images and counteracts their original purpose.

Much of the principled ethical rejection of any engagement with perpetrators receives its thrust and momentum by taking the victims' perspective. In the many cases in which this perspective is an assumed ethical-theoretical stance and not inhabited by a particular individual victim, there is a tendency to generalize on behalf of all victims. While many victims and victims' communities do question this engagement, this is not the case for all. Jacques Semelin reminds us that in genocides it is often the perpetrators who reject attempts at understanding: "It is this primacy of apparent incoherence [of the violence] as imposed by the executioners that turns the desire to understand into a moral obligation" – a moral obligation that is precisely impelled by the victims' need for an explanation to the question of, quoting Holocaust survivor Primo Levi, "Why me?" (2007: 2). Indeed, the vast majority of the remarkable Cambodian documentaries Raya Morag analyses emerge from the victims' community who frame their engagements with perpetrators in explicitly ethical terms (Morag, 2020, see also Canet, 2019: 811).

We also need to consider the normative presuppositions of the question of why engage with perpetrators. The question places the burden of defense on those who do engage with perpetrators and thereby tacitly presupposes a default perspective of excluding perpetrators. But why *not* engage with perpetrators? Perpetrator exclusion is the default starting point even in Anthony Duff's philosophical argument, when he discusses how we can punish genocidal perpetrators given that they, as *hostis humani generis* (enemy of mankind), are outside the law and any normative community. Consequently, he argues that while he is skeptical about the possibility of a normative community encompassing all of mankind, we need such a holistic, normative conception of humanity in order to bring perpetrators into the fold of a normative community. However, the very exclusion of perpetrators as *hostis humani generis* already presupposes, concealed in the foreign Latin, a normative community of humankind: there is no enemy of humanity – a normative judgment – without presupposing the normative category of humanity (Duff, 2009). The default position of perpetrator exclusion likely stems from notions of retributive justice that unilaterally impose punishment on the perpetrators and remove them from society through imprisonment (Metz and Gaie, 2010: 278; Wenzel et al., 2008). Yet, different value systems are more inclusive of restoration and reconciliation as part of justice – such as the Rwandan *gacaca* (Clark, 2010: 220–256) – and involve perpetrators from the outset with punishments in the form of community-rebuilding labor. Indeed, Canet (2019) argues that engagement with perpetrators is a precondition for reconciliation.

An exclusion of perpetrators is also problematic, because there are cases – albeit rarer – that trouble the perpetrator victim binary and complicate the popularly held black-and-white picture of genocidal perpetration. Although genocide is preconditioned on a near complete power asymmetry between perpetrators and victims not merely as individuals but as an entire category, a simple asymmetric polarity between perpetrators and victims is not always present on the individual level – that is the level on which we (typically) negotiate questions of guilt and morality. Thus, Rithy Panh's *S21: The Khmer Rouge Killing Machine* (*S21, la machine de mort khmère rouge*, 2003)³ raises the difficult question what degree of responsibility should be accorded to Khieu Ches, who was aged twelve or

³ First mentions of a film will use English titles with the original-language titles in brackets. Subsequent mentions will use abbreviated English titles only.

thirteen at the time of his recruitment as guard for the torture prison S21, or to Nhem Ein who committed violence, because disobedience meant “you were dead for sure.” Yet, S21 survivor Vann Nath – a constant presence in the film – rightly problematizes perpetrators’ self-perception as victims by repeatedly questioning them whether they should occupy the same status as those they participated in torturing and killing (Boyle, 2009: 101). The former guards meet Nath’s questioning with silence in a partial reflection of the inadequacy of the binary categories of perpetrator and victim. A yet more extreme case is found in *Rwanda, the Hills Speak (Rwanda, les collines parlent, 2006)* where we meet François Karangari who survived as a Tutsi because, threatened by a Hutu kill squad, he killed his – already seriously injured – Tutsi brother. We witness his public confession – in front of his brother’s wife – at the local *gacaca* and a member of the kill squad confirms his story. While Karangari killed in order to preserve his life, the viewer watches uneasily as Karangari describes how he fell into a beating frenzy when clubbing his brother to death, and the following refusal of his brother’s wife to forgive him reflects the difficulties of reconciling the perpetrator with the victim in one person.⁴ Being confronted with the individual fates of perpetrators and perpetrator-victims enables us to examine uncomfortable but necessary moral questions of differing degrees of responsibility beyond simple binaries.

Historical and socio-political circumstances further exacerbate a simplistic exclusion of perpetrators from documentary discourse. The swift, Allies-imposed transition towards perpetrator delegitimization in post-Holocaust Germany paired with a near complete destruction and expulsion of the victim community during the genocide itself enabled the facile demonization and exclusion of perpetrators from official discourse, even while perpetrators were still hiding in Germany or, denying their past, occupied official positions in Germany (Paul, 2002: 16–20). Holocaust perpetrator delegitimization is apparent in Claude Lanzmann’s interviews with perpetrators that are almost exclusively filmed in secret and non-consensually (*Shoah*, 1985) or in the refusal of perpetrators, such as Erich Bartelmus, to be interviewed altogether in Marcel Ophuls’s *Hôtel Terminus* (1988). In contexts lacking perpetrator delegitimization, perpetrators have much less need to evade the cameras. The post-Holocaust circumstances in Germany are the exception and are thus not fully appropriate as a representational yardstick for post-genocide documentary representation (on the Holocaust as representational paradigm, see Jinks, 2016). In Cambodia, the Khmer Rouge waged a civil war for more than a decade and retained international representation at the UN until 1993 – long after the demise of the regime in 1979 (Fawthrop and Jarvis, 2005: 8–51) – and thereby enjoyed de facto impunity for decades. The current Khmer Rouge Tribunal is limited in scope given its only two successful convictions and Cambodian prime minister Hun Sen’s Khmer Rouge past. In Indonesia impunity reigns even today and any justice efforts are conducted and directed from abroad to ensure the safety of witnesses (Wieringa and Katjasungkana, 2019: 1–20). Engaging with perpetrators, injustice, and impunity as a constitutive part of these post-genocide societies – as Joshua Oppenheimer in his *The Act of Killing* (2012) and *The Look of Silence* (2014), and Rithy Panh in *S21: The Khmer Rouge Killing Machine*, *Duch: Master of the Forges of Hell (Duch, le maître des forges de l’enfer, 2012)* – is almost inevitable (see also Morag, 2020: 49–50), not least given that the victim’s perspective is discredited in the Indonesian context, where victims’ perspectives are discounted as coming from “scheming communists” (Oppenheimer in Canet, 2018: 160). These documentaries challenge the dominant paradigm of absencing perpetrator testimonies in documentaries on the Holocaust, where perpetrators are talked *about*, rather than with, and are commonly excluded as participants in the representational discourse from the outset. These

⁴ See also the kidnapped child soldiers in *Wrong Elements* (2017) who participated as perpetrator-victims in mass atrocities of Joseph Kony’s Lord Resistance Army.

documentaries' inclusion of extensive perpetrator testimony and perpetrators' present-day attempts to deal with their violent past not only enables a representation of perpetrators as complex human individuals (Alkan, 2020: 283), but also prevents a simple receding of these crimes into a concluded past. This need to engage perpetrators in still unfolding socio-political circumstances helps explain the frequent documentary encounters between victims and perpetrators in especially Cambodian documentaries – encounters which are “unimaginable in post-Holocaust European cinema” (Morag, 2020: xii) – and thereby challenge the normative interdictions established in the wake of the Holocaust (Boyle, 2015: 510–511). Even Rwanda that did experience a swift transition of power post-genocide faced the problem of extremely large victim and perpetrator communities living alongside each other in the second-most densely populated country in Africa.⁵ Thus, here too, documentaries reflecting on the aftermath of the genocide inevitably face a social fabric of which perpetrators form an inextricable part. Therefore a disproportionate number of documentaries on the aftermath of the genocide of the Tutsi engage with victims *and* perpetrators, such as Anne Aghion's *Gacaca Trilogy* (2002), Lukas Augustin's *Unforgiven (Unversöhnt)*, 2014, and Bernard Bellefroid's *Rwanda, the Hills Speak*. Indeed, perpetrators are engaged with through interviews even in documentaries with a dominant focus on the victims, such as Eric Kabera's *Guardians of Memory (Gardiens de la mémoire)*, 2004, who himself is a survivor.

As we have seen, few post-genocide societies are in a position to represent genocide without an active engagement of perpetrators. Furthermore, cultural factors in the respective post-genocide reconciliation efforts may not be premised on an ethics and justice of unilateral perpetrator exclusion. Binary contrasts between perpetrators and victims can lead to problematic exclusions of complex individual fates or even of entire groups that have managed to escape the perpetrator label. Ultimately, the call for such binary contrasts may itself be based on unquestioned ethical presuppositions that are dominated by the historical circumstances and representations of the Holocaust and thus set inadequate norms for the representations of genocides more generally.

Documentary as Historiography

Documentaries can take on many different forms and genres and documentaries on particular genocides may develop their own subgenres (for Rwanda, see Cieplak, 2017: 34–36). Concerning the Rwandan genocide, Cieplak especially considers firstly documentaries covering the lack of international response and secondly those focused on the post-genocide justice efforts. With regard to the Holocaust, Kerner follows Nichols' influential categorization of documentaries and especially discusses expository, observational, interactive, and poetic documentaries (Nichols, 2001: 99–138; Kerner, 2011: 177–242; for trends in recent Holocaust documentaries, see Prager, 2015). However, across my corpus of genocides and with respect to perpetrator representation, I contend there are two broad strands in documentaries which pose different but not mutually exclusive ethical challenges. Here, I will discuss the first such type of perpetrator representation, which I call historiographical, before discussing the second type that I term testimonial in the next section. Historiographical documentaries integrate perpetrator representation in a relatively rigorous and chronological narrative (which Nichols calls the “expository” documentary mode), whereas in

⁵ The most reliable estimates of those directly involved in killing vary between 175,000–210,000 or about 14% to 17% of the active adult male Hutu population (Straus, 2006: 117–118) and 367,000 representing about 19.5% (McDoom, 2022: 281–289). This contrasts with a perpetrator proportion of only about 1% of the adult male population in Germany with an estimated 200,000 perpetrators (Valentino, 2013: 36). On relative population density, see McDoom (2022: 47–50).

testimonial documentaries perpetrators are predominantly encountered in face-to-face interviews in a documentary narrative that dominantly relies on these testimonies (whether those of perpetrators or others).

Historiographical documentaries are typically impelled by a mandate to inform a broader public and often motivate – with varying success – similar ethical arguments as historians, namely that understanding is a necessary precondition to prevention. Thus, Michael Darlow, who filmed the “Genocide” episode of the television series *World at War* for the British channel *Thames Television*, programmatically states the purpose of the episode “not primarily [to be] a film about the suffering of people in the camps. It is an attempt to set down what happened and above all, why” (Darlow, 2005: 142). Similarly, Laurence Rees’ BBC television series *The Nazis: A Warning from History* has its pedagogical-ethical imperative inscribed in its title, while in an interview about his follow-up series *Auschwitz* (produced by the BBC and the American PBS), Rees re-emphasizes that “Without an understanding of how it happened, you can’t begin to look around the world and think why it might happen again” (PBS, n.d.). Such a response is also found in Michaël Prazan’s *Einsatzgruppen: The Nazi Death Squads (Einsatzgruppen, les commandos de la mort, 2009)*, produced by the French public television channel France 2, which ends with a harrowing note on the lack of prosecution of shooting squad perpetrators in Lithuania and Ukraine as well as Neo-Nazi amateur footage of modern-day killings in the style of the *Einsatzgruppen*. The implication of this footage and these appeals is that understanding is crucial to preventing the moral danger of becoming a perpetrator and that, conversely, a lack thereof leads to impunity and continued perpetration. Indeed, occasionally, documentaries can contribute to the prosecution of historically and legally overlooked perpetrators, as was the case with Hans Friedrich who openly professed anti-Semitism and admitted to killings of Jewish civilians (as part of the first SS-infantry brigade) in the documentary *Auschwitz* and promptly faced prosecution in Germany (Duke, 2005).

It is not surprising that many of these documentaries with their quite ostensibly pedagogical quest and moral suasion are frequently, but not exclusively, documentary series produced for and by television (and often public television). The serial television format allows for extensive historical arguments, witness testimonies, and archival footage. While this type of documentary is often permeated by mentions of the unimaginable and inexplicable Holocaust horrors, the scales nonetheless inevitably tip towards the explicable and understandable to which they have been predisposed by their expository character (Nichols, 2001: 33–34).

When measured against this ethical paradigm of producing understanding, documentaries need to balance the competing demands of complex causal explanation of structural historical patterns and public accessibility with its tendency towards more easily digestible explanatory means. Often this increased accessibility is achieved by focusing on major perpetrators in the format of “talking (heads) with Evil” (Morag, 2020: 16) and portrays historical processes as a consequence of intentions and decisions of powerful individual agents, or what E.H. Carr calls “Bad King John theory of history” (Carr, 1990: 45). Furthermore, historiographical documentaries tend to integrate any testimonies into a larger argumentative narrative. In the case of perpetrators, this instrumentalization of testimony abstracts from and collectivizes the question of individual culpability, given that they ultimately serve as a description of a historical phenomenon that transcends the individual perpetrator – especially when the narrative strands ultimately lead back to the (testimonially absent) major perpetrator and thereby suggest that normative accountability lies with the documentary’s “Bad King John.”

This tendency, while largely shared across the historiographical documentary format, is especially pronounced in Germany. Here, popular televised portrayals of perpetrators and the Nazi-era more

generally is almost monopolized by Guido Knopp who – as head of the editorial department for “Zeitgeschichte” (contemporary history) at the German public broadcaster ZDF from 1984-2013 – has advised on, produced, written, or directed dozens of episodes about this period (Ebbrecht, 2007: 36–43; several of them exceeding 7 million viewers or 21% of the viewership: Kansteiner, 2003: 643). Productions under the involvement of Knopp relate history almost exclusively biographically and enlist witness testimonies solely in service of their narrative about major perpetrators. Thus, in this narrative format, victims’ testimonies are often at risk of merely serving the documentary’s narrative arc traced by a major perpetrator’s personal history, while the interviewed perpetrators who service that same narrative arc are under little pressure to talk about their own specific involvements and views at the time. Knopp’s almost extreme fetishization of the major henchmen is all the more digestible for the German public, because it avoids the touchy subject of their broader involvement in the Holocaust (Ebbrecht, 2007: 41).

When compared to similar mass-appeal productions by public broadcasting, especially in the UK, this format of representing perpetrators stands out all the more in its German variant. Where Knopp’s productions make few distinctions between victim and perpetrator testimonies and only haphazardly correct perpetrators’ distortions and falsities (Näpel, 2003: 222–224), Rees’ *Auschwitz* and *Nazis* individualize the different testimonies (Ebbrecht, 2007: 48) and make a point of featuring critical follow-up questions posed to the respective perpetrator by the interviewer in precisely those moments in which perpetrator accounts of their personal involvement and morality are problematic.⁶ Despite a significantly more extensive use of reenactments in *Auschwitz*, the historical commentary and analysis is much more systematic, sober, and less obtrusively condemnatory than that of Knopp’s contemporaneous productions whose commentator continuously reminds us how terrible it was even if we find the rapid cutting against a backdrop of ominously screeching violins and kettledrums quite suspenseful – less terrible, but rather terribly entertaining.

The representation of Holocaust perpetrators has occasionally become more diverse and less Hitler-centric in its explanations. Rees’ *Auschwitz* made the commandant of Auschwitz Rudolf Höß its protagonist while also discussing the role of secondary and tertiary perpetrators, and Hitler only appears sporadically in the Knopp-produced *Holocaust* (2000). The increasing focus on “ordinary” rank-and-file perpetrators is even more pronounced in Michaël Prazan’s *Einsatzgruppen* and in Ruzowitzky’s *Radical Evil (Das radikal Böse)*,⁷ whose take-home message about the moral dangers of “ordinary viewers” becoming perpetrators resonate more than their “talking (heads) with Evil” documentary counterparts. However, both BBC and ZDF still return to the tried-and-true Hitler-centric approach with, for example, *The Rise of the Nazis* (2020) and Knopp’s production *Hitlers Manager* (2004).

Historiographical documentaries particularly seek to motivate, with varying success, the classic historical justification for engaging with perpetrators: to understand is to prevent. The risks are that the macro-level of examination overlooks the individual’s experience and – in the case of perpetrators – their accountability. Similarly, their treatment of historical events as a past that can be captured by an explanatory historical compass inevitably encourages approaching the past as

⁶ Almost all the documentaries discussed here, despite their otherwise very diverging formats, are more critical in probing their interviewees. See, for example, Marcel Ophuls’s ironic questions and remarks, the critical questions of Luke Holland’s interpreter when interviewing SS men and other perpetrators, or the confrontation of perpetrators with victims’ resentment which forms an integral part of Cambodian documentaries on perpetrators (*Final Account*, 2021; *Hôtel Terminus*, 1988; Morag, 2020).

⁷ These trends are in line with earlier developments in perpetrator research especially Christopher Browning’s book *Ordinary Men* which has been enormously influential (2001).

finished. The increasing use of reenactments may create a sense of suspense and drama of a history unfolding before the viewers' eyes (see Ebbrecht, 2007), and yet the very claim that we can draw conclusions and lessons from history presupposes that the past is, well, concluded. Testimonial documentaries, as we will see in the next section, treat the past as living on.

Testimonial documentaries and perpetrator representation

Extensive testimonial engagement with genocidal perpetrators is – with some important exceptions⁸ – an increasingly strong trend since the turn of the millennium, and it is this newer documentary tendency which has received prominent academic attention (Canet, 2019; Morag, 2020). Testimonial documentaries are somewhat more diverse in style than historiographical ones (typically they fall into Nichols's "observational" or "participatory" documentary categories; Nichols, 2001: 99–138). They are more internationally distributed on festival circuits and usually target a more culturally diverse audience. Directors and producers are more likely to be transnational (e.g. from diasporic communities such as the French-educated Cambodian genocide survivor Panh on Cambodia) or international (such as Franco-American filmmaker Aghion in Rwanda or American Oppenheimer in Indonesia). The result of this greater diversity in documentary production and targeting is that narratives are less likely to follow national boundaries of genocide reception – and boundaries pose a particular problem when genocides are not part of the shared cultural and historical heritage of the direction and production team or the target audience. While Euro-American historiographical narratives of the Holocaust are often at least to some extent localized and the narratives target a more specific national historical reception,⁹ the shared, albeit different, Euro-American experiences in the Holocaust mean that a certain national angle is not inherently problematic. However, such national angles become a problem when, for example, in the case of Rwanda, the only national narrative is effectively the lack of an existing national narrative. The catastrophic non-response by international powers to the Rwandan genocide, no doubt, is a valid point of critique, nonetheless it is problematic when this is the dominant narrative about the genocide – a narrative with Euro-America as its center, told through the perspective of and interviews with whites (predominantly US-Americans) – as is the case in *Ghosts of Rwanda* (*Frontline*, 2004) (Dauge-Roth, 2011: 74). We encounter similar problems when in *The Khmer Rouge: Power and Terror* (*Les Khmers Rouges: Pouvoir et Terreur*, 2001) an event as incisive as the Khmer Rouge's "evacuation" of Phnom Penh is only told from the perspective of French embassy staff, who were in fact evacuated, and not that from any of the city's 2 million inhabitants, for whom "evacuation" meant slave labor, executions, and mass starvation in the countryside. The imposition of a gendered lens with feminized or infantilized victims and masculinized perpetrators, criticized by Hirsch of photographic representations of the Holocaust (Hirsch, 2003) and by Holmes of the (largely historiographical) BBC productions on Rwanda led by white "male hero adventurer[s]" (Holmes, 2013: 184–197), poses further problems of reifying simplistic binaries and reproducing dominant Western cultural norms. Though such culturally fraught and biased perspectives are a problem faced by any form of documentary, testimonial genocide documentaries avoid it more often, not least because

⁸ E.g. *The Extermination of Jews* (*Der Judenmord*, 1998); *The Trial* (*Der Prozess*, 1984); *Shoah*, 1985.

⁹ Thus the British-American docuseries *Auschwitz* is localized in the familiar accent of the respective British (with Samuel West) and American audience (with Linda Hunt) and discusses the fate of Jews in the German-occupied Channel Islands (which are Dependencies of the British Crown), including collaborating British "bobbies," and the German "Holokaust" series (using deliberately Germanized spelling with a "k") focuses almost exclusively on German perpetration and mentions foreign collaboration only passingly (*Holokaust*, 2000).

filmmakers of this kind tend to spend significantly more time in the respective country or stem from it.¹⁰ Thus, in the testimonial documentary *Red Wedding*, Pon Sochon, female protagonist and survivor of the Khmer Rouge's systematic policy of forced marriage to and ensuing rape by cadres, undermines any possible stereotyped representation of the passive (and female) victim in her strong-willed search for and confrontation of the male and especially female perpetrators behind her forced marriage (Morag, 2020: 132–179).

In testimonial documentaries, we encounter individual perpetrators on a more personal level and they are given more screen time. This contrasts with the dominant representation of perpetrators in especially historiographical Holocaust documentaries, where (especially major) perpetrators often remain a distant Other. We experience the perpetrators, inevitably, as a person, arguably even in cases where the director is seeking to paint the picture of an evil Other. The form of the testimonial documentary is particularly politically powerful for several reasons: (1) Testimonial documentaries are especially common in contexts of transitional justice, and in these contexts, for better or worse, perpetrators need to be engaged with and confronted as accountable and responsible individuals (as opposed to madmen or evil Others from a historical past) in order to face moral and legal justice. (2) Since the testimonial format encourages us to experience the perpetrator as an individual who, in turn, typically talks about (or denies) their own involvement, we attribute notions of guilt and accountability predominantly to that particular perpetrator, not least because the narrative arc of testimonial documentaries is usually not in pursuit of tracing a larger, supra-individual historical trajectory. Thus, the testimonial documentaries' individualizing format makes deferral of guilt onto others structurally difficult for perpetrators. Especially in the rarer cases in which we encounter major perpetrators, the format inherently points out the hypocrisy when perpetrators, in their denials, make use of individualizing concepts of personal non-responsibility, while also having subjected their victims (but also lower-level perpetrators under their command) to destructive collective absolutes (e.g. race or class). Thus, in Sambath and Lemkin's *Enemies of the People* (2009) Pol Pot's reclusive second in command Nuon Chea denies any knowledge of (though accepts some responsibility for) the mass killings by the Khmer Rouge as does the intellectual party leader of the Khmer Rouge, Khieu Samphan, in Roshane Saidnattar's *Survive: In the Heart of the Khmer Rouge Madness* (2009) who furthermore insists on his non-responsibility.¹¹ Their claims of non-perpetration and personal non-involvement in a systematic killing apparatus are belied by the massive scale of the genocide that killed about a quarter of the population during their seat in high-office, while both documentaries in turn rightfully narrate and individualize the personal suffering of their respective directors under the regime in an effort to counter the de-individualizing processes of mass victimization in genocide. The testimonial format of the documentaries thus achieves a twofold reversal: a re-individualization of victims whom the genocide had de-individualized, and a re-individualization of perpetrator responsibility.

Despite their considerable power, testimonial documentaries in their dominant focus on individuals also face ethical problems. Inevitably the focus on the individual raises questions of representativeness and typically struggles to illustrate the supra-individual micro- and macro-processes of perpetration which have been the focus of perpetrator research (e.g. Browning, 2001; Hinton, 2004; Waller, 2002; Welzer, 2019; McDoom, 2022). Guilt and accountability are individual,

¹⁰ For example, Oppenheimer has spent 7 years in Indonesia and speaks fluent Indonesian, Aghion has repeatedly returned to Rwanda over the course of 7 years, while Thet Sambath, Panh and the filmmakers supported by Panh's production company Bophana are Cambodian.

¹¹ The documentary *Bitter Khmer Rouge (Khmers Rouges Amers, 2009)* is a peculiar mixture of historiographical and testimonial, given its overall narrative arc which traces that of the Khmer Rouge regime, but also its extensive testimonies of perpetrators, especially Khieu Samphan.

whereas structures of perpetration necessarily are not. An extrapolation from the level of the individual to the abstract systematic processes of perpetration can be fraught, and when testimonial documentaries seek generality they risk turning the individual into a symbol (e.g. the three loftily titled chapters 'Truth,' 'Justice,' and 'Reconciliation' of *Rwanda, the Hills Speak*, which each deal with a particular perpetrator's testimony at their *gacaca* trial). Thus, testimonial documentaries typically struggle to motivate the classic historical justification that to understand is to prevent, precisely because they foreground questions of individual responsibility.

While historiographical documentaries try to prevent a potential (genocidal) future, testimonial documentaries often, but not always, have an activist purpose to create change in the present (Canet, 2018, claims this activist purpose especially for Panh and Oppenheimer, but I believe it is a general characteristic of testimonial documentaries). This present is frequently a society in socio-political transition that is still in need to confront its past injustices. The testimonial documentary quest to change a transitional and often unstable present thus typically entails ethical problems much rarer in historiographical documentaries. Testimonial documentaries' focus on individuals in contexts of transitional justice can put their subjects – including perpetrators – in danger.¹² Perpetrator confessions can ensue revenge by former victims or reprisals even by members of the genocidal regime, if confessions happen in contexts and ways not condoned by whatever remnants of the genocidal regime still have sway. In Oppenheimer's *The Act of Killing*, the documentary's effective protagonist Anwar Congo, who murdered numerous people as part of an anti-communist purge in Indonesia 1965-66, demonstrates a highly conflicted relationship with his past. His various indications of remorse are at odds with Indonesian representations of this murderous history and put Congo (now deceased of natural causes) at risk of being silenced by other perpetrators.¹³ Undoubtedly, the political potential of testimonial documentaries to reframe previously accepted historical discourses relies on the destabilization of narratives of (non-)perpetration and its perpetrators. Directors therefore have to weigh carefully the advantages and negative consequences of exposing perpetrators through their documentaries.

A further common, but not always ethically unproblematic, element of testimonial documentaries is the non-consensual filming of perpetrators (e.g. *Red Wedding*, 2012; *Shoah*, 1985; *Hôtel Terminus*, 1988).¹⁴ The influential and very positively received example of Lanzmann's (*Shoah*, 1985) suggests that audiences condone the secret filming of perpetrators, rather than condemn it, and thus it largely avoids unintended sympathies of viewers on part of the perpetrators over the violation of the latter's rights. Nonetheless, there are ethical risks that are easily overlooked in this practice. Lanzmann's secret footage of Franz Suchomel over his role of handling incoming Jews and confiscating their valuables at the extermination camp Treblinka is arguably the most paradigmatic perpetrator interview in *Shoah* and succeeds in painting a picture of the unrepentant murderer, not least for Lanzmann's editing out those moments in the interview in which Suchomel seems to exhibit a troubled conscience (McGlothlin, 2020). Yet, in painting such a picture of Suchomel, Lanzmann not only turns Suchomel's willingness to cooperate against him, but also distorts the overall picture of

¹² An extreme case is Robert Kramer's documentary *Our Nazi (Nôtre nazi)*, 1984) that documents the making-of Thomas Harlan's fiction film *Exit Wound (Wundkanal)*, 1984) for which the nearly 80 year-old Nazi-perpetrator Alfred Filbert – previously convicted with a life sentence for the killings of 18,000 unarmed Jewish civilians, including children (Kay, 2016: 71) – was recruited to be constantly antagonized and held against his will when Harlan confronted him with Holocaust survivors, and allegedly had 5 ribs broken in the ensuing attempt to get away (Harlan and Stephan, 2011: 207).

¹³ Oppenheimer asserts that anger has been directed at him, rather than Congo himself (*Caroline M Cooper*, 2013).

¹⁴ The only historiographical documentary I know which secretly films perpetrators is *Einsatzgruppen* (2009).

Nazi perpetration in his film, where someone like Josef Oberhauser – third in command at extermination camp Belzec, with a much more significant role in the Holocaust than Suchomel (Arad, 1987: 28) – can largely get off the hook by his persistent and uncooperative silence and evasion of the camera. An exclusively testimonial focus can struggle to hold perpetrators accountable who stubbornly remain silent. Contrary to Lanzmann’s methods, Sambath chose to respect his promise to Nuon Chea and did not cooperate with judges of the Khmer Rouge Tribunal who requested his interview footage (O’Toole, 2010). When “represent[ing] a world of which one of the most salient characteristics is the negation of the individual’s will,” Sambath’s respect for individual wishes – even those of a perpetrator – can be an effective moral refutation of the structure of genocidal violence (Todorov criticized this with respect to Lanzmann’s film: Todorov, 1996: 276). Of course, Sambath’s choice is not without its own ethical challenges given that Nuon Chea had not been convicted. Nonetheless, in some cases filming without perpetrators’ consent provides the only way to hold them accountable for and through an audience. Thus, in Lida Chan and Guillaume Suon’s *Red Wedding* the hidden camera can catch perpetrators off-guard and capture their faces to provide the only permanent record of their personal responsibility, since they – unlike Lanzmann’s perpetrators who had all been convicted before *Shoah*, albeit with mild sentences – are likely never to be prosecuted for their crimes.

Engaging with perpetrators in contexts of transitional justice has risks. But it is in part because of these risks and the especial need to engage with perpetrators in such evolving contexts that make testimonial documentaries so powerful. They are often so impactful precisely because testimonies and confessions are not integrated into a pre-digested history lesson about the past. Instead, they frame and reframe testimonies and confessions as an inherently provocative political act unfolding in the present. In their testimonies the perpetrators evince the entire spectrum of confessional types Payne discusses in her seminal account of perpetrator confessions in Latin America (Payne, 2008): remorse, heroic confessions (asserting the act of perpetration as good), sadism, denial, silence, lies, amnesia, and betrayal (of other perpetrators). While the reception of the respective testimonial documentary is ultimately beyond the director’s control, they decide where and when the perpetrators appear before their camera, how they are framed and the space they receive in the edited film (on the significance of the “confessional stage,” see Payne, 2008: 22–24). Thus, they are in control over vital aspects of the perpetrator confession – even where they face perpetrators’ attempts to impose their own self-serving narratives and self-representations as in Oppenheimer’s *The Act of Killing* – and can thereby channel responses towards holding perpetrators morally accountable. They can document processes of (non-)reconciliation between survivor and victim – a common theme in documentaries on Rwanda,¹⁵ in *The Unforgiven* (2017) on the Bosnian civil war, and Oppenheimer’s *The Look of Silence* (2014). They can perform a post-genocidal power reversal between survivor and perpetrator, as Morag argues with respect to Cambodian documentaries (Morag, 2020: 16).¹⁶ And they can, as in Oppenheimer’s *The Act of Killing*, provocatively highlight continued impunity and let audiences “creat[e] another more morally forceful ending, where there is the possibility of victim recognition and a space where perpetrators are punished” (Hill, 2021: 814–15). They have an activist potential by reframing perpetrator discourses and thereby seek to transform the views of their audiences and societies.

Conclusion

¹⁵ *As We Forgive*, 2009; *Gacaca Trilogy*; *My Neighbor, my Killer (Mon voisin, mon tueur)*, 2009; *Unforgiven*.

¹⁶ For example, *Duch*; *S21*; *Red Wedding*; *Enemies of the People*.

Documentaries draw on several justifications of engaging with perpetrators. Explaining and, ultimately, learning from genocide for future prevention cannot be done without studying perpetrator motivation and the processes of violence as well as the gradual mechanisms of victimization. Furthermore, in many post-genocidal societies undergoing various transitions of justice, grappling with perpetrators is not merely a task of courts and historians – though they are integral – but effectively and inevitably of the entire society. What exact justification for its engagement with perpetrators it pursues and how it represents them depends on a highly complex set of factors, including personal and national backgrounds of the directorial and production team, the targeted audience and its national and social make-up, as well as the genocide and its aftermath with its specific cultural and historical characteristics. Nonetheless, I've argued that two main types of perpetrator engagements in documentaries stand out. Historiographical documentaries typically seek to reach a broad Western public distinguished by national criteria and therefore tailor their perpetrator focus to this perspective. Their pedagogical and didactic trajectory often explicitly endorses the ethical imperative that to understand is to prevent. Such understanding in the audience is fostered with varying success and explanatory models. Often, though not inevitably, the documentaries' description of major perpetrators' biographies are explicative surrogates for much more complex processes of perpetration with agents that are more diverse in their demographic background and contribution to genocide than the focus on the most exemplary and powerful perpetrators can reveal. Exceptions, however, exist (e.g. *Auschwitz; Radical Evil; Die Wahrheit über den Holocaust (The Truth about the Holocaust)*, 2014; *Einsatzgruppen*). The representation of the past as explicitly historical almost inevitably treats it as concluded, and present-day interviews with perpetrators (or victims) often merely service the supra-individual narrative arcs of history pursued by historiographical documentaries. In cases of uncertain historical heritage of the genocide and transitional states of justice in its aftermath, documentaries hence often choose a different format of representation – I have called them testimonial – for which perpetrator confessions (effectively always alongside victim testimony) are a goal in itself. Testimonies and confessions in these documentaries are treated as having the potential to impact present-day socio-political transformations and the aftermath of the genocide is not a concluded event but an unfolding reality. Testimonial documentaries are thus inherently more activist and their engagement with perpetrators is frequently driven by an ethical imperative to catalyze social and political changes and redress injustices. This activist motivation is perhaps most explicit in Oppenheimer's two films on the 1965-66 Indonesian mass killings (and his many subsequent interviews across the world) in a country that has still not faced its genocidal past. But even testimonial documentaries that engage with perpetrators less provocatively (and controversially) present us with barely forgiven, unreconciled, or unjust pasts – pasts, in other words, that are not finished and inherently require change.

Here, I have attempted to give a systematic discussion of the ethics of perpetrator representation and outlined two broad categories of documentary engagements with perpetrators of genocides that face different but not mutually exclusive ethical challenges. There are doubtlessly documentaries that do not easily fall into either category of documentary. Furthermore, in my efforts to systematize I have not been able to address the individual differences of perpetrator representations across each genocide, which can vary considerably especially along the axes of race, gender, class, and political ideology. A comprehensive discussion of these and their ethical challenges remains the task for future research. Nonetheless, it is clear that future research will have to consider perpetrators and their representations more fully than has been the case. The expulsion of perpetrators from society and its discourses post-genocide is rarely possible – or desirable given that entire categories of perpetrators, such as the *Wehrmacht*, can hide under their occluding demonization (Paul, 2002: 17). They are an integral part of a society's social fabric after genocide,

not least due to the sheer scale of mass violence, and therefore cannot and should not be ignored. Thus, ethically, they need to be engaged to understand how mass violence comes about and to hold them accountable as societies transition. And they need to be ethically engaged, carefully balancing competing demands of perpetrator exposure, safety, and justice, for documentaries to participate in, rather than shut down, discourses on genocide.

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